

Variation of the Charge of Copper Ferrocyanide Hydrosol in Presence of Electrolytes and Non-electrolytes

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The investigations on the cataphoretic velocity and coagulation of different hydrosols (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 296 ; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Raichoudhury, *ibid.*, 1927, 4, 493 ; Mukherjee, Raichoudhury and their coworkers, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 697, 735) produced results not in harmony with current theories on coagulation of colloids in several aspects and it was felt desirable to carry out similar experiments in the case of copper ferrocyanide hydrosol (*cf.* Duclaux, *J. chim. Phys.*, 1907, 5, 29 ; 1909, 7, 405 ; Pappada, *Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 9, 137 ; Sen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 517, 539 ; Mehrotra, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 142, 345 ; Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1527).

Dependence of the Cataphoretic Velocity on the Method of Preparation of the Sol.

It has been established in the case of arsenic sulphide and ferric hydroxide hydrosols that the cataphoretic velocity depends on the method of preparation of the sol (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *loc. cit.*; S. N. Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 53, 159 ; 1930, 52, 13), and hence different samples of hydrosols of copper ferrocyanide were prepared and their cataphoretic velocities studied. First, the hydrosol of copper ferrocyanide was prepared by precipitating copper ferrocyanide from copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with conductivity water till peptisation occurred. The peptisation occurred at a pH value of about 7.5 of the supernatant liquid. The sol obtained in this way is very dilute and in order to obtain a moderately concentrated sol, a few c.c. of a dilute solution of potassium ferrocyanide were added to peptise a given amount of the precipitate. The sol,

so obtained, was subjected to dialysis, till the dialysate gave no test for ferrocyanide. With the progress of dialysis, measurements of cataphoretic velocities were taken. An equiconducting solution of potassium chloride was found suitable as the upper liquid, as the potential gradient before and after passage of the current remained constant within 5%, the direct and reverse readings being also correct within the same percentage of error as shown by the following data in Table I. *In this as well as in subsequent tables V always denotes the velocity in cm. per sec. per volt per cm. multiplied by 10^5 .*

TABLE I.

Samples.	Direct		V	Reverse		V
	Pot. gradient in volts per cm.			Pot. gradient in volts per cm.		
	Before	After		Before	After	
1	0.338	0.813	41.8	0.799	0.845	39.2
2	1.157	1.154	44.9	1.105	1.184	40.8

It will be seen from the Table I that though the potential gradient is not absolutely constant, the variation is not such as to affect the general trend and is within what one obtains in usual measurements of cataphoretic speed unless special care is taken in selecting the upper liquid. One notices that there is always a greater variation with the current reversed. The values for the cataphoretic velocity of the sol with dialysis are given below.

TABLE II.

Days of dialysis.	V			Equicoagulating conc. of KCl.
	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	
0	39.2	41.8	40.5	1.01N
7	44.9	40.8	42.8	1.015
20	45.9	43.8	44.9	0.98
30	50.4	48.4	49.4	0.92
60	43.7	43.2	43.45	0.85

The results show that on dialysis, the cataphoretic speed increases at first and then decreases with progressive dialysis. The coagulating concentration of potassium chloride remains constant for about a week and then diminishes. This observation is not in harmony with the idea that the cataphoretic velocity and the stability of a sol always go hand in hand. Sols designated afterwards as type A were prepared in the above way.

Since by the above procedure, it was found that the sol even after continued dialysis contained appreciable amounts of potassium ferrocyanide, we adopted a different procedure. The precipitate of copper ferrocyanide, obtained from equivalent quantities in solution of copper chloride and potassium ferrocyanide (Weiser, *loc. cit.*), was mixed thoroughly with pure conductivity water and centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was replaced by fresh conductivity water and the process repeated about seven times. After the fourth washing, the precipitate begins to peptise. After two to three further washings, conductivity water was poured very slowly over the precipitate in the centrifuge tube and the clear water, drawn by a pipette, when tested for chloride or ferrocyanide ions was found to be free from them. These precipitates were then mixed with a suitable quantity of water so as to peptise the whole quantity of precipitate and a somewhat dilute sol was obtained. The electrical resistance of the freshly prepared sol was found to be about 10,000 ohms. The resistance decreased rapidly and within one day attained a value of about 6000 ohms. Measurement of the cataphoretic velocity was undertaken with equiconducting potassium chloride as the upper liquid. But here as will be found from the Table III given below, the potential before and after passage of the current was not constant. In this case a few drops of dilute potassium hydroxide solution was added to a solution of potassium chloride such that the conductivity, and p_H of this mixture are equal to those of the hydrosol coagulated with solid KCl. The p_H of the hydrosol was measured by the colorimetric method after coagulating the sol with the least amount of solid potassium chloride. It is also of interest to note that with (KOH + KCl) mixture as the upper liquid, the potential gradient was found to be fairly constant when the current was first passed for about 15 to 20 minutes before taking the actual readings, and the direct and reverse readings were found to be correct within an accuracy of about 5%.

TABLE III.

Upper liquid.	Direct.			Reverse.		
	Pot. gradient	V.		Pot. gradient	V.	
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.	
(1) Equiconducting KCl	0.964	0.912	38.2	0.898	0.952	54.4
(2) Equiconducting mixture of KCl & KOH	0.869	0.836	44.3	0.886	0.912	40.9
	0.850*	0.774	43.7	0.898	0.917	43.4

Sols prepared in the above way are designated henceforward as type B. It was soon observed that this sol on keeping showed clear sedimentation at the bottom. The sol was therefore centrifuged and the cataphoretic velocities of centrifuged and non-centrifuged sols were measured and compared. It was found that (Table IV) centrifuged sols have a little less cataphoretic velocity and they were always found to be more conducting.

TABLE IV.

Nos.	Before centrifuge			After centrifuge		
	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
1	53.6	48.8	51.2	48.4	48.0	48.2
2	46.5	43.9	45.2	42.5	38.3	40.4
3	51.8	48.6	50.2	48.6	45.4	47.0

The data given in the above tables show the dependence of the cataphoretic velocity of the particles of the different sols on the method of preparation.

Effect of Some Simple Electrolytes and of Centrifuge on the Cataphoretic Velocity of the Sol.

Effect of some simple electrolytes and centrifuge in their presence on the cataphoretic velocity of copper ferrocyanide hydrosol (in one case type B and in another type A) has been studied. Results are given in the following tables, where *C* denotes the concentration

¹ Potential measurement was taken just after the passage of the current.

of the electrolyte in normality and V denotes the cataphoretic velocity multiplied by 10^5 as usual. Results in Table V have been obtained with sol No. 2 (*vide* Table IV) after centrifuge and those in Table VI from a sol of type A, *i.e.*, the sol contained a moderate amount of potassium ferrocyanide. From these tables it is clear that the variation of the cataphoretic velocity with the concentration of the electrolyte depends also on the previous treatment of the sol. It is singular that in Table V, in the case of a centrifuged sol whose initial cataphoretic velocity is low, an initial rise is always observed in the cataphoretic velocity (even with the bivalent barium ion) with a gradual decrease afterwards, whereas in Table VI, with a non-centrifuged sol (containing free potassium ferrocyanide) the cataphoretic velocity first decreases and then increases with yet another drop afterwards. The sol obtained by centrifuging shows a diminution of the cataphoretic velocity in presence of an electrolyte. The higher the concentration of electrolytes taken, the greater is the effect observed.

TABLE V.

Copper ferrocyanide hydrosol (type B).

Electrolyte.	C	V							
		...	0	0.0002	0.0005	0.001	0.002	0.01	0.02
KCl			40.4	44.5	50.4	47.3
NaCl			40.4	46.4	49.9	48.5
HCl			40.4	42.4	44.3	40.4
BaCl ₂			40.4	43.4	39.4	35.4

TABLE VI.

Copper ferrocyanide hydrosol (type A).

C.	V			
	Potassium chloride		Sodium chloride	
	Before centrifuge.	After centrifuge.	Before centrifuge.	After centrifuge.
0	51.2	48.2	51.2	48.2
0.001	47.3	45.3	48.5	45.5
0.0025	44.5	40.2	45.5	41.5
0.025	48.4	37.2	50.2	39.2
0.05	42.4	39.4	46.2	35.8

Effect of Dilution of the Sol in Presence and Absence of Potassium Ferrocyanide.

It has been shown by the author (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1231) that the cataphoretic velocity of a hydrosol of copper ferrocyanide decreases on dilution. This sol was prepared by precipitating copper ferrocyanide from concentrated solutions of copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide. The precipitate was washed with conductivity water by decantation for about one month. Part of the precipitate was peptised. It was then subjected to dialysis for about two months. A portion of this sol was diluted and measurements were taken. Another sol was prepared as stated before, *but dialysis was continued for a month*. The results are given in Table VII. These results suggest that the difference in the behaviour of these two types of sols is caused by the amount of potassium ferrocyanide present in the sol. Accordingly cataphoretic velocities were determined with dilution of sols, which contained initially very little free potassium ferrocyanide, in presence of increasing amounts of potassium ferrocyanide solution and the results given in Table VIII, clearly show that the behaviour of the cataphoretic velocity of the copper ferrocyanide hydrosol depends on the amount of potassium ferrocyanide initially present in the sol.

TABLE VII.

Dilution (sol :H ₂ O) pure sol ...		1 : 1	1 : 3	1 : 7	1 : 10	1 : 31	1 : 79
V _c {	Sol I ...	70·6	50·9	45·3	—	29·9	—
	Sol II ...	56·95	—	—	54·3	—	52
						52	50·15

TABLE VIII.

Sol.		V at dilution of			
		Pure sol.	1 : 1	1 : 4	1 : 9
N-K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .					
I	0 c.c.	45·2	40·4	37·4	33·4
II	1	57·2	56·4	53·4	50·1
III*	10	53·4	50·4	49·3	51·4
IV*	20	45·2	40·5	46·4	44·5

* In the U-tube, above the boundary there was formed light yellowish layer of liquid with the passage of the current indicating the migration of ferrocyanide ions above the boundary.

In Table IX are given results at different dilution of the sol in presence of varying concentrations of potassium chloride. These results show once more that when the initial cataphoretic velocity of a sol is low, the addition of electrolytes increases its value (which is sometimes followed by a decrease) depending on the amount of copper ferrocyanide present.

TABLE IX.

Dilution ratio.	V at a concentration C of KCl.				
	0	0.001	0.002	0.01	0.02
1 : 1	40.4	44.5	46.5	50.4	47.2
1 : 4	37.4	45.2	48.3	49.3	60.3

Effect of Some Non-electrolytes on the Cataphoretic Velocity.

Lastly the behaviour of the cataphoretic velocity of copper ferrocyanide hydrosol has been followed in presence of sugar and ethyl alcohol, as also its variation in presence of potassium chloride and barium chloride. The results given in Tables X, XI and XII have been obtained with a sol of type A (*i.e.*, it contained a moderate amount of free potassium ferrocyanide).

TABLE X.

Copper ferrocyanide sol, potassium chloride and ethyl alcohol.

EtOH %.	V at the concentration C of KCl.							
	0	0.002	0.004	0.01	0.02	0.025	0.033	0.05
0 c.c.	54.3	...	49.3	49.5	...	40.06
2.5	50.8	41.0	...	45.6	39.1	...
10	46.1	31.8	36.1	46.3 (32.0) after coagulation
20	41.7	35.3	34.4	30.1

Here, to start with, the initial cataphoretic velocity was high, and as usual, in presence of potassium chloride the cataphoretic velocity at first decreases, then increases with a final drop afterwards. In presence of sugar alone, the cataphoretic velocity at first decreases rapidly, but the rate of variation of the velocity with higher percentages of sugar is small. The rate of variation of the velocity with increasing concentrations of potassium chloride is smaller, the higher the percentage of sugar taken, *i.e.*, smaller the initial cataphoretic velocity of the sol.

TABLE XI.

Copper ferrocyanide sol, potassium chloride and sugar.

Sugar %.	<i>V</i> at the concentration <i>C</i> of KCl.				
	0	0.004	0.0125	0.025	0.05
0 g.	54.3	49.3	46.1	49.5	40.06
2.5	44.7	...	42.7	55.7	35.6
5.0	42.0	...	41.6	44.5	32.0
10	41.7	...	39.1	40.8	The sol coagulated

TABLE XII.

Copper ferrocyanide sol, barium chloride and sugar.

Sugar %.	<i>V</i> at the concentration <i>C</i> of BaCl ₂ .				
	0	0.0001	0.0002	0.0005	0.001
0 g.	54.3	38.9	36.2	34.8	31.0
2.5	44.7	39.55	28.1	...	20.8
5	42.8	44.3	31.05	...	25.1
10	41.3	47.3	44.1	...	The sol coagulated

With barium chloride alone, the velocity continually decreases; in presence of 2.5 % sugar, the same behaviour is observed though the initial drop is low and the final drop high compared to the velocities observed in case of barium chloride alone. In the case of 5 and 10 % sugar, we find an initial increase in the velocity of

the colloid in presence of barium chloride. In presence of ethyl alcohol alone, the cataphoretic velocity diminishes; with increasing concentrations of potassium chloride, the cataphoretic velocity at first diminishes, increases afterwards and finally there is another drop in the velocity. In the case of 20% ethyl alcohol, there is always a decrease but here of course, the velocity could not be followed up to those concentrations of electrolytes where we observe an increase in other cases.

DISCUSSION.

On the Relation between Cataphoretic Velocity, Potential of the Double Layer and Density of Charge.

Two main peculiarities are noticeable from curves in Figures 2, 4, 5, 6, and 7 in the case of uni-univalent salts in absence of non-electrolytes:

(1) First, when the initial cataphoretic velocity is low, *i.e.*, about 40×10^{-5} cm. per sec. per volt per cm. there is an initial increase with a gradual drop afterwards.

(2) When the initial cataphoretic velocity is high, we get a minimum followed by a maximum or a characteristic \cup shaped curve.

FIG. 1.

Effect of dialysis.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Effect of dilution.

FIG. 4.

Effect of dilution in presence of increasing conc. of KCl.

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

Effect of ethyl alcohol and KCl.

FIG. 7.

Effect of sugar and KCl.

FIG. 8.

Effect of sugar and BaCl₂.

Kruyt and Willigen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, **139**, 170), in order to explain coagulation at the high cataphoretic speeds observed in the case of uni-univalent salts, maintain that the potential is low, though the corresponding speed is high due to a higher dielectric constant. Starting from the equation,

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta u}{D} \quad \text{or} \quad \zeta D = 4\pi\eta u = 4\pi U_1$$

(where U_1 = the cataphoretic speed after viscosity correction, ζ = electrokinetic potential, D = dielectric constant) they have advanced the view that the increased dielectric constant of the electrolyte is responsible for the higher cataphoretic speed observed at the high concentrations of electrolytes (uni-univalent) following the work of Furth (*Physikal. Z.*, 1920, **25**, 676) and Pechhold (*Ann. Physik*, 1927, **83**, 427) on the variation of the dielectric constant of solutions of electrolytes in which it was shown that the dielectric constant shows first a small decrease followed by a sharp increase afterwards as the concentration of the electrolyte is increased. It follows from their arguments that the potential of the double layer is proportional to U_1/D . The validity of this relationship can be better studied in presence of non-electrolytes alone. Now it has been already shown by Mukherjee and his coworkers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 704) in the case of arsenious sulphide sol that an increase or a decrease of the dielectric constant on the addition of the non-electrolyte sometimes

produces the same effect—a lowering of the cataphoretic speed. The potential of the double layer is then apparently not determined by the change in dielectric constant alone. It is also not justified to assume a direct proportionality between density of charge and dielectric constant (*cf.* Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry" 1926, p. 463). Assuming that the dielectric constant of the colloidal solution changes in the same proportion as pure water with the addition of a non-electrolyte, it will be seen from the following table that the ratio of cataphoretic velocity of the colloidal copper ferrocyanide to the dielectric constant is not constant (the values D , have been obtained by interpolation from the data of Harrington, *Phys. Rev.*, 1916, 8, 581) a fact which disproves that the variation of the dielectric constant *alone* is responsible for a variation in the cataphoretic speed of the sol.

TABLE XIII.

Sugar %	...	0	2½	5	10
V	...	54.3	44.7	42.8	41.3
D	...	80.4	78.25	77.0	76.2
V/D	...	0.67	0.57	0.55	0.54

Further comparing the curves in presence of electrolytes in Figs. 2 and 5, it is apparent that for the same concentrations of potassium and sodium chlorides, there is observed in one case an increase and in another case a decrease in the cataphoretic velocity of the colloid. Moreover, centrifuging the sol in presence of high concentrations of electrolytes cannot evidently change the dielectric constant so much as to lower the cataphoretic velocity to such a low value as actually observed. It is also clear that the final decrease in the velocity at very high concentrations of electrolytes in some cases and the initial rise followed by a drop in others with lower concentrations cannot be explained on the basis of the change of the dielectric constant alone (*cf.* Figs. 2 and 5). These considerations show also that the observations mentioned above are not even explicable from the point of view of Kruyt and Briggs (*K. Proc. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1929, 32, 384), who point out that the variation of the dielectric constant in the bulk of the solution need not be considered but only that in the interface should be taken into account, in order to explain the very high cataphoretic speed observed at high concentrations of electrolytes. Moreover, this latter proposition appears to overlook the

considerations of Debye and McAulay (*Physikal. Z.*, 1925, 28, 22), who have shown that round an ion the distribution of the water molecules would not be materially altered by molecules of lower dipole moment. In other words, the dielectric constant of the water layer surrounding free charges would be materially determined by the strongest dipoles. If the argument of Debye and McAulay hold good and this appears to be obvious enough, the above explanation appears to be insufficient.

It is then obvious that the charge may be affected by other factors than dielectric constant alone. There is evidence to show that a direct relationship exists between the amount of excess of adsorption of an ion of one sign and the rate of cataphoretic movements. Lamb's equation has as its basis (*Brit. Assoc. Rep.*, 1887, p. 495), a relation connecting cataphoretic velocity and surface density of charge. An increase in the density of charge certainly denotes an increase in cataphoretic speed, since the coefficient of sliding friction changes in the same sense as the density of charge (Lamb, *loc. cit.*). In Helmholtz's treatment also the fundamental factor determining the electrical force involves the volume density of charge. From arguments due to Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 705), it appears more plausible to explain these observations by assuming that either the density of charge is changing or preferably both the density and the thickness of the double layer are changing. The great effect of cane sugar (Table XIII) points to the conclusion that the variation in the density of the charge is predominant. The interpretation of cataphoretic velocity in terms of the density of charge from the point of view of ionic equilibrium at the solid liquid interface is therefore to be preferred.

An Explanation on the Basis of a Change of the Density of Charge from Mukherjee's Theory of Double Layer.

It is, however, possible to conceive a simple picture of these processes in terms of the density of charge on the basis of the views of Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103) on the nature of double layer. A colloidal particle in its process of formation adsorbs chemically a certain species of ions on its surface and thus acquires its charge. In consequence of the charge, ions of opposite sign will be drawn near the surface—some of which are bound and some are free depending on the kinetic energy of these ions. The charge, imparted to the colloidal particle is due to the number of primary ions still remaining

uncovered. *Now it is clear that just as the primarily adsorbed ions exert forces of attraction on the oppositely charged ions in the liquid to get them fixed or bound to the surface, so ions in the liquid similarly charged to that of the colloid exert an attractive force on these bound ions and try to pull them towards the interior of the solution. Whether an ion will be bound or not will depend on the relative magnitudes of these two opposing forces.* The origin of the charge of the colloidal copper ferrocyanide is usually ascribed to the preferential chemical adsorption of ferrocyanide ions during the process of formation of the colloid. The cataphoretic velocity or the density of charge will be low,

Firstly (1) when the colloid initially contains traces of potassium ferrocyanide (*i.e.*, ferrocyanide ions) and therefore adsorbs chemically only a few ferrocyanide ions per unit surface of the colloidal particle; in consequence, a large number of places on the surface of the particles where ferrocyanide ions could be chemically adsorbed are vacant and hence the surface of the colloidal particles might be said to be "unsaturated." These conditions are realised in a sol of type B.

(2) Secondly either, (a) when the sol contains very high concentrations of potassium ferrocyanide (before dialysis, *cf.* Fig. 1), or (b) by increasing either only the number (with the addition of a non-electrolyte of low dielectric constant, *cf.* Figs. 6, 7, 8 or with the addition of potassium salts) or both the number and valency (with the addition of other electrolytes) of the bound ions when the sol initially contains moderate amounts of potassium ferrocyanide (initial cataphoretic velocity high—a sol of Type A), *i.e.*, when the surface of the colloidal particles had almost been "saturated" due to the primary adsorption of ferrocyanide ions.

Variation of the Charge with Simple Electrolytes.

In both the cases mentioned above when the initial density of charge is low, the number of similarly charged ions that can approach near about the interface will be comparatively high and that of the oppositely charged ions will be relatively low, and thus there is a greater probability of initial increment of charge [in case (1) due to the primary chemical adsorption of similarly charged ions and in case (2) owing to the removal of bound ions as a result of attraction towards the interior of the liquid by the

similarly charged ions to that of the colloid]. If the initial cataphoretic velocity is low due to condition (1) as in a sol of type B where traces of potassium ferrocyanide are present, low concentrations of electrolytes (specially uni-univalent salts) will increase the charge due to the primary chemical adsorption of negatively charged ions as the surface of the particles are unsaturated (here chlorine ions; see Figs. 2 and 4). With increasing concentrations of electrolytes as the charge tends to be higher and higher, more oppositely charged ions are attracted and similarly charged ions repelled with the result that at higher concentrations of electrolytes the cataphoretic velocity diminishes again. With very low concentrations of barium chloride there is an initial increase in the density of charge; thus even the bivalency of barium is not sufficient to counteract the primary chemical adsorption of chlorine ions, perhaps because of the tetravalency of the primarily adsorbed ions. Had the primarily adsorbed ion been monovalent, there would have been less chance of observing this increment in charge with a bivalent cation. Subsequently however the drop is much steeper as is to be expected (*cf.* Fig. 2).

When the initial density of charge (*i.e.*, cataphoretic velocity) is high (curves obtained without centrifuge and 0% non-electrolyte in Figs. 5—7,—these sols were of type A which contained moderate amounts of free potassium ferrocyanide), obviously there will be at first a diminution as more of the oppositely charged ions will be attracted; but as the charge becomes lower, the number of similarly charged ions will be comparatively greater near about the surface and exert their influence in removing the bound ions (primary chemical adsorption of anions is less probable here, first because of "saturation" of the surface due to the primary adsorption of ferrocyanide ions and secondly because of attractive forces exerted on them when they pass through a layer of oppositely charged bound ions and repulsive forces due to primarily adsorbed ferrocyanide ions) resulting in actual increment of charge at these high concentrations of electrolytes. It is to be noted that appreciable coagulation has taken place at these concentrations of electrolytes and smaller particles are combining to form larger aggregates in which process the mutual repulsive forces between the bound ions themselves will be brought into play. Moreover, the change in the curvature resulting from aggregation may also modify the charge (Alty, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1924, 106. 1). It is therefore to be expected that in this

region of coagulation when by centrifuging the larger aggregates are thrown down and separated, the cataphoretic velocity acquires a low value (Fig. 5). As the density of charge tends to be high, a greater number of oppositely charged ions will be attracted and thus there will be observed a final decrease. With barium chloride the first diminution is very sharp, but as the density of charge tends to be low, the effect of similarly charged ions comes into play with the result that at higher concentrations, the curve is almost flattened (Fig. 8, 0% sugar). No increment is observed here at the coagulating concentrations probably because of the higher valency of the barium ion.

Variation of the Charge with Dialysis and Dilution.

It is not difficult also to understand the nature of the curves (Figs. 1 and 3) obtained on dialysis and on dilution in presence of potassium ferrocyanide. On dialysis with decrease in the concentration of potassium ferrocyanide first the number of bound potassium ions decreases, thus increasing the density of charge and therefore the cataphoretic velocity. When the concentration of potassium ferrocyanide becomes appreciably low, it is conceivable that there occurs a decrease in the number of the primarily adsorbed ferrocyanide ions, so that finally there is a decrease in the cataphoretic velocity. On dilution of the sol in absence of potassium ferrocyanide, the cataphoretic velocity decreases thus showing a diminution in the number of primarily adsorbed ferrocyanide ions; in presence of small concentrations of potassium ferrocyanide, the density of charge diminishes but not so markedly as in its absence, for here the decrease in the number of primarily adsorbed ferrocyanide ions cannot be so marked due to the presence of greater number of ferrocyanide ions. With sol III, there is at first a decrease with an increase afterwards while with sol IV, in addition to this there is a final decrease though not so prominent. With dilution as the cataphoretic velocity tends to be low, the number of ferrocyanide ions (for the concentration of potassium ferrocyanide is high) that can approach near enough the surface also increases with the result that the velocity afterwards increases again. The final decrease shows that as the density of charge increases, more oppositely charged ions are attracted and adsorbed as bound ions.

Variation of the Charge with Non-electrolytes.

The effect of non-electrolytes can also be understood from the above standpoint in a general way. Addition of pure non-electrolytes will decrease the dielectric constant of the medium and thus depress also the cataphoretic velocity due to the increase in the number of bound ions (Figs. 6—8, sols of type A). The activities of the ions present will also change due to a change in the dielectric constant with the addition of a non-electrolyte (Debye and Hückel, *Physikal. Z.*, 1923, **24**, 305, 385). Recent researches on the activity coefficients of ions in aqueous solutions of non-electrolytes by Brönsted and Williams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1338), Hansan and Williams (*ibid.*, 1930, **52**, 2759), and others (Lucasse, *ibid.*, 1926, **48**, 626 ; Scatchard, *ibid.*, 1927, **49**, 217) have in general shown the quantitative verification of the theory of Debye and Hückel in very dilute solutions of electrolytes. In the following (where high concentrations of electrolytes are generally used) it is sufficient to know in a qualitative way that as the dielectric constant decreases the activity coefficient and therefore the activity of ions also decreases. It is seen (Fig. 8) that at 2½% sugar, an initial rise is not observed in the velocity as barium is bivalent and is thus probably able to compensate for the increased number of similarly charged ions that can approach near enough the double layer. In this connection the difference between the removal of bound ions and the chemical adsorption of primarily adsorbed ions is to be noted, both resulting in an increment of charge (*cf.* also Fig. 2). The density of charge is a little higher in presence of 2½% sugar (44.7×10^{-5} cm. per sec. per volt per cm. as compared to 40.4 expressed in the same units in Table V, Fig. 2). This may perhaps account for the absence of initial increment here. From 2½% to 5 and 10% sugar, the number of bound ions available for removal is higher, as is evidenced by the low cataphoretic velocity. Comparing the results with 5% and 10% sugar, it is seen that the initial rise in the velocity is higher in the case of 10% sugar. Though both the number of similarly charged ions that can approach near enough the surface and the number of bound ions are slightly higher at 10% sugar solution and may account for the higher initial rise, it is better to keep in view in this case the variation in another factor, namely, in the activity of the barium and chlorine ions with the addition of sugar. In considering this variation, it is to be borne in mind that for each barium ion, there are two chlorine ions and it is possible that the activities of these

ions may change due to the formation of some BaCl and Cl ions in addition to the change in the dielectric constant. In this way the proportionate decrease in the concentration of free barium ions (and therefore in the activity) would be greater than that in the number (and activity) of free chlorine ions, and this effect would be greater, the higher the percentage of sugar taken. That some such consideration is necessary would appear also from the results obtained with this sol and potassium chloride in presence of sugar (*vide* Fig. 8, sol of type A). At a higher concentration of the electrolyte, the rise is most marked, though it gradually diminishes with higher percentages of sugar. Considering individually the curve at a particular percentage of sugar, the results are explicable as they show the usual decrease with increase afterwards and a final drop in the velocity, except in the case of 10% sugar where measurements could not be proceeded with high concentrations of electrolyte due to coagulation. The curves however tend to be more and more flattened at lower concentrations of the electrolytes, and the first lowering becomes less and less pronounced as higher percentages of sugar are taken. With even 10% sugar (when the cataphoretic velocity is 41.3×10^{-5} cm. per sec. per volt per cm.) and 0.125N-KCl there is no increment. The activities of potassium and chlorine ions are expected to be diminished in the same proportion so that for a particular percentage of sugar unless the concentration of free chlorine ions (*i.e.*, potassium chloride) is high, a rise in the charge is not observed (*cf.* with BaCl_2). Thus it appears that when the surface of the colloidal particle remains saturated (due to the adsorption of maximum number of primarily adsorbed ions) the initial increment in the charge may not be observed even if the density of the charge is low. Hence, the effect of the primary chemical adsorption of similarly charged ions in increasing the charge is seen to be more pronounced than that of the removal of bound ions when other factors such as activities of ions as in the case of barium chloride do not interfere. It is to be noticed that at 0.025N potassium chloride, the velocity shows an increase in absence of sugar; if 2½% sugar is added, the rise also is most prominent, as here the number of similarly charged ions increases greatly (since by addition of 2½% sugar alone, the drop in the velocity is high, *i.e.*, from 54.3×10^{-5} to 44.7×10^{-5} cm. per sec. per volt per cm.) but the diminution in the activity of potassium ions is expected to be less, compared to that in the case of higher percentages of sugar.

A relatively greater diminution in the activity of potassium ions combined with higher attractive forces for oppositely charged ions and greater repulsive forces for similarly charged ions due to a greater lowering of the dielectric constants perhaps account for the diminution in charge at higher percentages of sugar in presence of 0.025*N*-potassium chloride.

It is noteworthy that with ethyl alcohol (Fig. 6) and potassium chloride the results are not exactly similar to those in presence of sugar. With ethyl alcohol alone, the density of charge is not so much diminished as in the case of sugar, showing that the number of bound ions (here potassium ions from free potassium ferrocyanide in the chloride) does not increase so much due probably to the comparatively lower activity of potassium ions in presence of ethyl alcohol on account of a greater diminution of the dielectric constant. Moreover, the great diminution of the mobility of potassium ions in presence of ethyl alcohol (Ulich, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, **23**, 390) is possibly also to a certain extent responsible for this behaviour of the colloid. Curves with 0% and 2.5% ethyl alcohol in Fig 6 separately considered show the usual \cup -shape as the density of charge is initially high. Curve with 10% ethyl alcohol shows first a decrease with an increase afterwards, whereas that with 20% ethyl alcohol shows always a decrease, for in these two cases experiments could not be proceeded with due to coagulation setting in. Ethyl alcohol decreases the dielectric constant more than sugar and also the initial density of charge, to start with, was higher except in the case of 20% ethyl alcohol; so that the force with which the oppositely charged ions are bound and similarly charged ions repelled in this medium is stronger with the result that there is not only no increment, but on the other hand it is seen that the rate of initial diminution of the cataphoretic velocity of the colloidal copper ferrocyanide with concentration of potassium chloride is higher, the higher the amount of alcohol taken. With higher concentration of electrolytes the subsequent rise is also higher, the higher the percentage of alcohol taken except in the case of 20% alcohol where it is not possible to measure the velocity at these concentrations of electrolytes. In the case of 10% ethyl alcohol the colloid after partial coagulation shows a lower density of charge. This is also easily explicable from the point of view developed above. In the case of 20% ethyl alcohol, though the initial density of charge is low, there is no initial rise obviously due to the very great lowering of

dielectric constant, with the result that the similarly charged ions are repelled and the oppositely charged ions are bound with a comparatively much higher force. Thus all these considerations show that only under certain conditions, an initial increment in the charge is possible. Possibly besides the change in the dielectric constant of the medium and the activities of ions with the addition of these non-electrolytes, there is also a variation in the thickness of the double layer, in the mobilities and the apparent radii of the ions concerned—but our knowledge about these properties is not sufficient to warrant discussions on such a basis in detail.

CONCLUSION.

In this paper an attempt has been made to explain the different types of results on cataphoretic velocity, in presence of electrolytes and non-electrolytes essentially on the basis of the double layer as conceived by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*). While these considerations are sufficient to indicate at least qualitatively the nature of the curves showing the variation in the cataphoretic velocity of a colloid in presence of electrolytes and non-electrolytes it is realised that in view of the absence of relevant data on the dielectric constant of mixtures of electrolytes, colloids and non-electrolytes, any quantitative explanation is not possible. But though limited in this way, it has been shown (on the assumption of a proportionate variation in the dielectric constant of the colloid as that of water on the addition of a non-electrolyte) by taking into consideration other factors than dielectric constant, that an initial rise in the cataphoretic velocity of colloids is possible even without the chemical adsorption of similarly charged ions or any increase in the dielectric constant (*cf.* Fig. 8 with BaCl_2). A strong possibility has also been pointed out that increment of cataphoretic velocity of a colloid does not always indicate an increment of charge due to the chemical adsorption of ions similarly charged to that of the colloid. From these considerations it is also possible to conceive a simple mechanism of the displacement of a bivalent ion by a monovalent ion or of cationic antagonism in the case of negatively charged hydrosols (the cataphoretic velocity is increased with the addition of a salt with monovalent precipitating ion when the density of the charge has already been diminished by a salt with bivalent precipitating ion as observed by Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Raichaudhury, and the

increment ascribed to the displacement of a bivalent ion, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 493). All these results on the cataphoretic velocities and particularly those near about the coagulating concentrations of electrolytes and their interpretations show that it is not now possible to think of coagulation taking place at a critical potential both from the theoretical and experimental points of view, and that equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes do not always depress the charge of the colloidal particle to the same extent and that the adsorbability and the coagulating power of a precipitating ion cannot always go hand in hand, as first pointed out by Wo. Ostwald (*Kolloid Z.*, 1920, 26, 28).

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